

Mercaptocoumarinoxazoles. Part-V[†]. Synthesis of 2-[[[(Aryl/Heteroaryl)carbonyl]methyl]thio]-4,8- dimethylpyrano[3,2-*f*]benzoxazol-6(*H*)-one Derivatives

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2-Mercapto-4,8-dimethylpyrano[3,2-*f*]benzoxazol-6(*H*)-one (**2a**) has been prepared by treating 6-amino-7-hydroxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (**1**), with CS₂ in alkaline medium. The reaction of **2a** with various aryl/heteroaryl halomethyl ketones gives 2-[[[(aryl/heteroaryl)carbonyl]methyl]thio]-4,8-dimethylpyrano[3,2-*f*]benzoxazol-6(*H*)-ones (**2b-f**), which upon oxidation yield the respective sulphones (**3b-f**). The structures have been confirmed by analytical and spectral data.

MERCAPTOOXAZOLE¹ and coumarin² derivatives have been found to possess a widerange of medicinal and commercial importance. In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis of mercaptooxazoles fused at (7,8)³, (6,7)⁴, (5,6)⁵ and (3,4)⁶ positions of coumarin derivatives which are found to be associated with appreciable biological activities⁷, we now report the synthesis of 2-mercapto-4,8-dimethylpyrano[3,2-*f*]benzoxazol-6(*H*)-one derivatives (**2** and **3**).

a = H

2-Mercapto-4,8-dimethylpyrano[3,2-*f*]benzoxazol-6(*H*)-one (**2a**) has been prepared by the interaction of 6-amino-7-hydroxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin

(**1**) with carbon disulphide in presence of methanolic KOH. The structure of **2a** was established on the basis of elemental analysis and ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data. The reaction of **2a** with various aryl/heteroaryl halomethyl ketones in the presence of either anhydrous ethanolic KOH or anhydrous ethanol and dimethylformamide, gave the respective 2-[[[(aryl/heteroaryl)carbonyl]methyl]thio]-4,8-dimethylpyrano[3,2-*f*]benzoxazol-6(*H*)-ones (**2b-f**). The products obtained by these two methods were shown to be identical (m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra). Better yields are achieved by using dimethylformamide and ethanol. The ir spectrum (KBr) showed strong bands at 1 700–1 740 (lactone C=O) and 1 670–1 690 cm⁻¹ (ketone C=O).

The structure of **2b** was confirmed by ¹H nmr spectrum (in CDCl₃), where C₈- and C₄-methyl protons were found as singlets at δ 2.4 and 2.5 respectively, CO-CH₂ adjacent to S⁸ as a singlet at δ 4.9, C₇-proton as a singlet at δ 6.2 and six aromatic protons as complex multiplet at δ 7.2–8.1. The mass spectrum of **2b** showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 365 (*M*⁺, 30%) and other peaks at *m/z* 247 (10%), 218 (87), 105 (100), 90 (18), 77 (20), along (*M*+1) and (*M*+2) peaks. The ratio of intensity of isotopic peaks confirms the presence of the sulphur atom. By the oxidation with hydrogen peroxide⁹ in the presence of acetic acid, these compounds (**2b-f**) were converted to the corresponding sulphones (**3b-f**). The products were confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data; the ir spectral (nujol) contain an additional band at 1 340–1 320 cm⁻¹ due to the sulphone group¹⁰.

† See Ref. 6.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer-282 instrument, ^1H nmr spectra on a Varian 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a JEOL-JMS-300 spectrometer at 70 eV. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

2-Mercapto-4,8-dimethylpyrano[3,2-f]benzoxazol-6(H)-one (2a): A mixture of 6-amino-7-hydroxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin¹¹ (1; 0.01 mol), CS_2 (10 ml), KOH (0.02 mol), methanol (40 ml) and water (10 ml) was refluxed for 30 h. It was then cooled and on acidification a solid slowly separated out. It was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (2a; 70%), m.p. 290° (Found: C, 58.3; H, 3.65; N, 5.43; S, 12.78. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ requires: C, 58.2; H, 3.64; N, 5.6; S, 12.8%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1740 (lactone C=O), 1510 (N=C=S), 1070 (C=S)¹², 1640, 1600, 1450, 1410, 1380 and 1180 cm^{-1} ; (oxazole ring)¹³; δ (CDCl_3) 2.2 (3H, s, C_8-CH_3), 3.16 (3H, s, C_4-CH_3), 3.57 (1H, s, exchangeable SH), 6.26 (1H, s, C_7-H) and 7.18 (1H, s, C_6-H); m/z 247 (M^{+} , 100%), 220 (10.5), 219 (71.7), 218 (28.9), 186 (6.8), 161 (9), 131 (5.4), 109 (5.4), 105 (8), 103 (8.6) and 77 (12.9).

Reaction of 2a with aryl/heteroaryl halomethyl ketones. General procedure (Method 1): 2a (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol containing KOH (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aryl/heteroaryl halomethyl ketone (0.01 mol) was added and refluxed for about 4 h. It was then cooled, and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from suitable solvent (2b-f; 60-70%) (Table 1). **Method 2:** A mixture of 2a (0.01 mol), the appropriate aryl/heteroaryl halomethyl ketone (0.01 mol), dry

ethanol (15 ml) and dimethylformamide (15 ml) was refluxed for about 5 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed thoroughly with water and recrystallised from suitable solvent (2b-f; 65-70%).

Oxidation of 2b-f: The respective compounds (2b-f; 0.02 mol) were dissolved in acetic acid (20 ml) H_2O_2 added (5 ml; 30%, w/v), and the reaction mixture was warmed on a water-bath for about 1 h. The solid sulphones (3b-f) were separated on dilution with excess of water. The compounds were filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from suitable solvents, (70-80%) (Table 1).

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p.** °C	Mol. formula
2a	70	290	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2\text{S}$
2b	70	205	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_4\text{S}$
2c	63	210	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}$
2d	65	208	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_6\text{ClS}$
2e	65	215	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_6\text{S}$
2f	68	220	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_6\text{S}$
3b	80	240	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_6\text{S}$
3c	72	245	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}$
3d	74	249	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_6\text{ClS}$
3e	78	246	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_7\text{S}$
3f	70	250	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_7\text{S}$

*C and H analyses of all compounds found satisfactory. **2b-f were recrystallised from acetone while the rest from aqueous ethanol.